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Cognitive Stylistic Component of Socio-Cultural Activity Manager Training

Abstract: *Introduction.* The relevance of the study is due to the need to train managers with a systemic adaptive ability to operate with technologies, knowledge, and information, the ability to change and adapt to new needs of socio-cultural reality in terms of integration into the global information space. *Purpose and methods.* The purpose of the article is to determine the cognitive and stylistic features of the manager's personality, substantiate their role in his professional formation and development in the learning environment. The methodological basis is the principles of scientific knowledge (determinism, system, development), the provisions of activity, system, and personality-oriented approaches. *Results.* The researchers systematized scientific approaches to the cognitive styles' definition, substantiated their role in professional development and manager's personality development. Cognitive styles are defined as cognition strategies, cognitive-stylistic dimension of personality, which determines the ways of setting and solving problems, decision-making and goal-setting. The psychological parameters and characteristics of cognitive-stylistic features are singled out, the factors of cognitive-stylistic development of the manager's personality in the training conditions are determined. *Conclusions.* The scientific novelty consists in concepts' definition of professional formation cognitive-stylistic component and the manager's personality development and in highlighting the optimal parameters and characteristics of cognitive styles for its successful functioning. The practical significance of the study is to reveal

the possibilities of applying knowledge about cognitive and stylistic features in the learning optimization, cognitive activity development of the socio-cultural sphere managers.

Keywords: cognitive style, cognitive-stylistic component, educational and cognitive activity, cognitive sphere, professional formation and personality development, manager, socio-cultural activity.

1. Introduction

The problem formulation. Currently, the needs of the socio-cultural industry in terms of integration into the global transformational information space determine the importance of high-level professional managers with the established systemic adaptive ability to operate the relevant technologies, knowledge, and information, to modernize professional practices, to change and adapt to new labor market needs and rapid decision-making. Meeting this challenge will contribute to the development of professional and personal qualities, competencies and increase the efficiency of a manager's professional activity ready to implement innovative professional tasks, who is motivated to continuous professional and personal self-improvement, to increase their professional competence. In this regard, it is necessary to recognize a timely appeal to the problem of cognitive personality development throughout life, namely, the improvement of training programs for managers of a socio-cultural sphere, taking into account their individual and personal characteristics. One of the conditions for effective management in the field of socio-cultural management is the ability of professionals to have a holistic vision of human resource management, which combines standardized organizational technologies, as well as patterns of understanding the individuals and groups behavior, the ability to think creatively and adapt to any situation.

The future managers' education should take into account the young people age characteristics (early maturity), namely: almost sufficient level of self-awareness and responsibility to actively and effectively participate in planning, creating favorable learning conditions, evaluating and correcting the learning process, understanding the learning purpose and ways to implement the acquired knowledge, skills, abilities, personal qualities, and values, etc. (Hurch, 2006; Sheiko, 2009; Kostyuchenko & Dykhnych, 2016; Kostiuchenko, 2017, 2018a, 2018b, 2018c, 2019). Instead of simple forms of knowledge transfer from teacher to the listener, the priority form of learning is the development of skills to find the necessary information to solve any complex problems. In terms of domestic psychology (Kostiuk, 1989; Maksymenko, 2006; Polishchuk, 2007; Tokareva & Shamne, 2017, etc.), the central new growth of the specified age

category is personal and professional self-determination, which appears as need to realize the place in society, to understand yourself and your capabilities, as well as a sense of professional competence. In Western psychology, to denote this phenomenon, the concept of “identity” is used (Erikson, 2006, p. 59). Identity is an individual conscious self-identity, which allows the individuals to perceive themselves in their relation to the environment and determines the system of ideals, life prospects, values, social roles with appropriate behavior forms. The new growths in the cognitive development of student youth are independence, dialectics (Riegel, 1975, 1979) (ability to comprehend opposing ideas, synthesizing them and integrating the ideal and the material, potential and relevant, real and fantastic) and critical thinking; flexible transitions in the interrelationships of figurative, logical and active components (Vygotsky, 2003); ability to learn something new; conceptual relativism (tolerance for different views on the problem), arbitrary attention; selective memory; intellectualization of memory using mnemonic techniques.

State study of the problem. Solving the problem of professional development and personality development of the future manager of the socio-cultural sphere is represented in the works of modern scientists and practitioners (Hurch, 2006; Sheiko, 2009; Ponomarenko, 2012; Lysakova, 2013; Olenina, 2013; Kostyuchenko & Dykhnych, 2016; Hryhorchuk, 2018; Martynyshyn & Kovalenko, 2018; Bryl, 2018; Dyba, 2018; Petrova, 2019, etc.). Currently, in the education field of future managers, there is a need to optimize the learning process, the factors of which are cognitive and stylistic features of their personality concerning creativity and creative thinking (Guilford, 1958; Torrance, 1964; Vygotsky, 2003; Ermolaeva-Tomina, 2001; Moliako, 2004, 2007, etc.).

Applied research has identified and analyzed the cognitive styles features that: reflect the individual specifics of intellectual processes, improve the learning process based on some models (Gardner et al., 1960; Kagan, 1966; Wardell & Royce, 1978; Royce & Mos, 1980; Witkin & Goodenough, 1982; Kolb, 1985; Honey & Mumford, 1988; Sternberg, 2001; Galiakberova & Galyamova, 2019; Zhang et al., 2020), used to process information about the environment at several levels from perceptual to metacognitive (Kozhevnikov, 2007), affect the background emotional difficulties in reaching a compromise in information processing during decision-making (Wang & Maguire, 2018); record individual ways of cognition (Broverman, 1960; Gardner et al., 1960; Kagan, 1966; Witkin & Goodenough, 1982; Klaus, 1987; Kornilova & Paramei, 1989; Kholodnaya, 2004, etc.). These cognitive styles are interrelated: with different situations and environmental conditions (Liedtke & Fromhage, 2019), with personal characteristics (Bondar, 2016; Broverman, 1960; Gardner et al.,

1960; Guilford, 1958; Dorfman et al., 1998; Klaus, 1987; Kutsenko, 2002; Naprasna, 2004; Romanovska, 2005; Skorynina, 2000; Studenikin, 1999; Witkin & Goodenough, 1982; Kholodnaya, 2004, etc.); affects various aspects of human behavior (Dorfman et al., 1998; Morosanova, 2010, etc.); provide opportunities to predict the peculiarities of communication and personal activities in the field of education, work (Tolochek, 2013; Kholodnaya, 2004, etc.).

Based on different scientists' definitions in the context of our study, we interpret the concept of “cognitive styles” as interpersonal differences in information processing, cognition strategies, cognitive-stylistic dimension of personality depending on the characteristics of its cognitive organization. The above-mentioned term determines the ways of setting and solving problems, decision-making and goal-setting, promoting the professional development and development of the future manager of socio-cultural activities, which involves planning, coordination, and the processes control carried out by the subjects of socio-cultural activities.

The solution to the aforementioned problems is essential, acquiring value not only in psychology but also in other sciences, culture, politics, economics, including modern business and management. The importance of these problems is due to the increasing demands of the social environment to the formation and implementation of the management cognitive component in the socio-cultural sphere with such components as effective operation of relevant technologies, knowledge, and information, non-standard vision of new opportunities for professional functioning and development, original ideas production, thinking flexibility and behavior.

Unresolved issues. It should be noted that the study of the cognitive and stylistic component of personality remains a relevant and debatable topic in various applied fields: education, psychology, psychotherapy, management, and more. Modern psychological and pedagogical technologies do not take into account the greater importance of cognitive styles for academic achievement than general abilities (Sternberg, 2001), as well as the role of the cognitive-stylistic component in the professional formation and development of the manager's personality as an interactive construct which develops under socio-cultural, educational, professional and other relevant requirements of society. However, studies of the socio-cultural activities managers' training peculiarities on a cognitive-stylistic basis in the domestic scientific literature are still insufficiently covered. Cognitive-stylistic factors need to be empirically identified as predictors of individual and professional success in special situations of communication and management activities, career guidance, counseling, conflict management, staff and project team members' selection, etc.

2. Purpose and methods

The purpose and research tasks. The purpose of the article is to determine the cognitive and stylistic features of the socio-cultural activities manager's personality in the learning environment and substantiate their role in the professional formation and development of the manager's personality.

According to the purpose, the following tasks of research are defined:

- to carry out the theoretical analysis, systematization, and generalization of scientific researches results of the person cognitive and stylistic features;
- to determine the components of cognitive and stylistic development of the manager's personality;
- to identify psychological parameters and characteristics of cognitive styles in the cognitive competencies of the socio-cultural sphere manager.

Methodology and methods. The methodological basis of the study is: 1) at the philosophical level – the basic principles of scientific knowledge: the principle of determinism, which necessitates the studied phenomenon explanation of the human psyche based on the natural interaction of external and internal factors available to empirical control; the principle of systematization, according to which the studied phenomena are known depending on the internally connected whole formed by them with the acquisition of new properties inherent in the whole; the principle of development, which allows us to study changes in psychological phenomena concerning the causes that give rise to them; 2) at the general scientific level – the main approaches of modern science: the activity approach to the study of the human psyche (L. Vygotsky, A. Leontiev, S. Rubinstein, etc.); system approach (I. Blauberg, V. Sadovsky, B. Yudin, etc.), including the study of individual differences (K. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya, B. Ananiev, A. Bodalev, B. Lomov, B. Merlin); personality-oriented approach to personality development (A. Maslow, J. Allport, K. Horney, etc.); 3) at the specific scientific level – psychological theories and concepts: human mental activity theories (V. Nebilitsyn, D. Bogoyavlenskaya, V. Petrovsky, A. Matyushkin), the functional systems theory by P. Anokhin, the concept of cognitive styles as metacognitive abilities by M. Holodnaya, system-stylistic research of T. Guseva's cognitive activity, principles of scientific cognition (determinism, systematics, development), the activity position, system, and personality-oriented approaches, from the standpoint of which the phenomenon of cognitive style is considered in the context of students' cognitive-educational activity; in the system, as internally connected with the whole with the acquisition of new properties characteristic of the whole; in the development

of the integral individuality of the future manager with the requirements of socio-cultural reality.

To achieve the purpose and implement the study objectives, the authors used such general scientific theoretical methods as analysis (including retrospective analysis of philosophical, socio-psychological, psychological, and pedagogical research), synthesis, systematization, and generalization of theoretical positions on cognitive styles in the vocational education system. Also, the study represents specific scientific methods of terminological analysis, conceptual and semantic characteristics of cognitive styles, specification of the most established concepts that reflect the ideas' formation about the cognitive-stylistic component functioning in the professional development and development of the future manager of socio-cultural activities.

Information base. The obtained results are based on: 1) theoretical and methodological developments presented in the publications of scientists in the socio-organizational-psychological direction, in particular in monographs, dissertations, specialized periodicals, collections of scientific conferences; 2) empirical results of long-term observations, surveys during the teaching of disciplines “Psychology”, “Management Psychology”, “Negotiation”, “Organization and direction of fashion shows”, “Producing”, “Management of fashion industry enterprises” in students majoring in “Manager of socio-cultural activities” at the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Theoretical analysis of the problem of cognitive-style development of the future manager's personality in the training environment

The emergence of the “cognitive style” concept (Gardner, 1953) in line with cognitive psychology is associated with the dominance of ideas about the personality traits relationship and the individual behavior identity. These terms are manifested in the features of perception, understanding, and explanation by a person of what is happening, which led to a desire to combine with the help of this phenomenon the psychology of cognitive activity and personology.

The cognitive style as a theoretical construct includes both the interaction of cognitive and personal components when the subject solves a problem situation and explains the personal factor that cognitive structures are part of the personality structure, which provides individual stability of cognitive style as a way of cognition and activity. The psychology of cognitive processes in the first place puts forward the differential-psychological aspect, namely: the

study of individual specifics of information processing, which is generally defined as a cognitive style. Individual differences in the methods of obtaining and reproducing information, the methods of analyzing and structuring their environment, in turn, form some typical forms of cognitive response, concerning which groups of people are similar and different from each other (Kornilova & Paramei, 1989, pp. 140-147). Therefore, the concept of cognitive style is used to identify both inter-individual differences in information processing and types of people depending on the characteristics of their cognitive organization.

In Ukrainian psychological science, the problem of cognitive personality style was investigated: as a cognitive-stylistic dimension in psychological works (Maksymenko & Pasichnyk, 2010; Palii, 2011; Kalamazh, 2012; Bodnar, 2016; Fedotova & Kulchytska, 2020; Kostruba, 2020 and others); in connection with various aspects of activity and personality: communication: manifested in the characteristics of the other people and oneself image, thereby influencing behavior (Studenikin, 1999) and communicative activity (Bondar, 2016); with the educational activity of students (Naprasna, 2004; Kalamazh, 2012), with intellectual and mental activity, abilities, cognitive processes (Maksymenko & Pasichnyk, 2010); as a factor: memory development (Skorynina, 2000), formation of personality cognitive experience (Kutsenko, 2002), the text comprehension process (Romanovska, 2005), professional development (Zherdetska, 2006), intellectual potential development (Pisotskyi, 2008).

The concept of “style” in the form of a global psychological parameter was interpreted as a style of studying reality. There are three directions of the term “style” formation, which are denoted as stages of individual identification, cognitive specification, phenomenological integration (Guseva, 2009). In a narrower sense, “cognitive style” was used to identify and specify a special kind of individual features of intellectual activity, which could not obtain an adequate theoretical interpretation within the traditional psychology of cognition. This concept was interpreted as: 1) a method of cognitive analysis which preferred (Witkin et al., 1962); 2) a relatively stable system of cognitive control principles, which provide the possibility of individual realistic-adaptive forms of reality reflection. Those systems act as an indirect link between the individual intentions and the objective situation requirements (Gardner et al., 1960); 3) the profile of mental abilities (Broverman, 1960); 4) stable features of the higher-order, which steadily affect how the cognitive and affective processes of personality manifest themselves (Wardell & Royce, 1978). The link that combines thinking and personality and reflects the degree of differentiation of the affective from the individual combines individual differences of motivational-necessary and perceptual order (Witkin & Goodenough, 1982). A

hypothetical construct that reflects the cognition strategies, ways (forms) of perception, thinking, and actions of the subject, which cause individually stable and in this sense personal characteristics of solving cognition problems in different situations, but mainly in situations of uncertainty; its severity changes during the ontogenetic development of a human, but remains constant in each individual if we compare its indicators with the level of the age group (Klaus, 1987, p. 13). Procedural (instrumental) characteristic of intellectual activity, which determines the method of obtaining a particular cognitive product; bipolar dimension is described by referring to two extreme forms of cognitive response; a time-stable characteristic of the subject, which is manifested at different levels of cognitive functioning (Kholodnaya, 1989).

Cognitive style is interpreted through the individuality category as: “stable individual features of cognitive strategies, formal characteristics of individuality” (Kholodnaya, 1989, p. 21); “individual psychological features of cognitive processes, the tendency to use inherent human ways of interacting with information, the actualization of individual-specific cognitive structure of the individual, which mediates the processes of information management at all levels of the cognitive sphere” (Dorfman et al., 1998); “personal formations that have a significant generalization and are manifested in a wide range of behavioral acts, which is the basis for their interpretation as personal factors of high order” (Karpov, 2004); a peculiar result of the interaction of the cognitive and personal component of the subject, which directly affects the formation of ways of setting and solving problems, decision-making and goal-setting (Zherdetska, 2006); determinants of personality traits (Palii, 2011); cognitive component of professional socialization of the individual in educational institutions (Moskalov, 2015); cognitive component of psychological readiness to work in a staff team (Karamushka et al., 2012).

Thus, in domestic science, the principle is the statement that the individual style of activity manifests itself in cognitive processes as a cognitive style, that is, a stable set of individual differences in the ways of perception, remembering, and thinking, behind which there are various ways of acquiring, accumulating and processing information. Cognitive style has an indirect effect on the organization of interaction between personality and the environment, providing a relationship between the cognitive, affective, and social spheres of the personality. A feature of modern studies of cognitive styles is the dominance of attention not on the meaningful characteristic of the person's cognitive activity (“what” thinks?), but on the ways of an organization (“how” thinks?) and strategies (which way?). At the same time, the individual methods of obtaining, processing and broadcasting information about the surrounding world, typical for each individual, come to the fore.

3.2. Components of cognitive and stylistic development of the future manager's personality

Cognitive development is one of the main ways of a young person's existence, determines his success in professional self-realization, and has definite features. In this regard, it is advisable to conduct a theoretical analysis of key individual psychological features that affect the perception of translated knowledge in the process of educational and cognitive activity.

The combination of cognitive and stylistic features with the dominance of certain personality traits, namely creativity, reflectivity, sensuality, activity, is associated with increasing the success of educational activities (Romanovska, 2005). Several other researchers indicated the trend of increasing academic success with increasing style flexibility, achieving cognitive style mobility (Kholodnaya, 2004; Guseva, 2009). Namely, studying the concept of cognitive personality style, we deal with the consideration of the creativity phenomenon, which is the basis for the professional formation success and the manager implementation.

In the context of this problem, in adapting the manager to the ever-changing conditions of communicative and managerial activities, in particular at the stage of its planning, with its information sets, a significant place is given to creativity. This is evidenced by V. Moliako (1994) opinion: "It is necessary to take into account the creative and transformative function of consciousness, the strategic organization of consciousness, which allows to streamline the consciousness content, find in chaos specific systems, design and build them, focusing on objective indicators, which are set by all those requirements that exist in reality" (p. 37). It is management strategies (Martynyshyn & Kostiuchenko, 2018) that condense the structures responsible for situation analysis, new information evaluation, research objects selection, reference points selection, allow to organize "chaos of thinking" and find means and ways of such ordering that will promote solving new management tasks, completing the creative process by achieving balance, harmonization.

One of the productive and creative thinking indicators is the flexibility of the existing cognitive abilities use and variability – versatility as the activation in certain circumstances of figurative, logical, and effective thinking and their elements optimal combination, ensuring the use of all cognitive abilities (Craig & Baukum, 2006; Bogoyavlenskaya & Susokolova, 2006 and others). In the context of our study, we highlight other creativity criteria that affect the success of various activities, including cognitive-educational: the ability to produce fundamentally new unusual ideas, to differ in thinking from the usual schemes, to solve problems in unusual ways; the ability to sharpen the perception

of shortcomings in knowledge, missing elements, disharmony (Torrance, 1964). Another considerable criteria are experience openness, sensitivity to new problems; categorization breadth, associations remoteness, associative series breadth; the ability to move quickly enough from one category to another, from one solution to another; independence, unusualness, wit of the decision (Ermolaeva-Tomina, 2001); speed (number of ideas that arise per time unit) and originality (ability to generate new ideas) thinking; susceptibility (sensitivity to unusual details, contradictions and uncertainties, willingness to flexibly and quickly switch from one idea to another) (Savchyn, 2007); metaphoricity (the tendency to use symbolic, associative means to express thoughts, the ability to see the complex in the simple, in the complex – simple) and metaphorization as an independent type of cognitive activity (a dynamic process that leads to a dynamic state of knowledge about the world, because the value obtained and at the same time the associative imagination caused by it, as well as non-linguistic entities that are not compatible at first glance, take part in this process) (Kostiuchenko, 2019).

Intentional experience is based on the students' intellectual abilities, which form the subjective criteria for choosing a subject area, the direction of finding a solution to the problem, information sources, ways to process it. In the structure of a young person's intellectual abilities, there are convergent and divergent abilities, as well as cognitive styles. Convergent is the ability of an individual to use logical thinking in solving normative problems with the help of definite combinatorial and procedural properties of intelligence in regulated situations and characterizes the adaptive capabilities of individual intellectual behavior in regulated conditions. Divergent abilities are creativity – the ability to generate a variety of original ideas in unregulated activity conditions based on multidirectional, independent of the laws of formal thinking logic. Cognitive styles are the individual ways of coding and processing information, formulation and solution of the intellectual problems, cognitive attitude to events and the world in general; cognitive styles system: information coding styles, cognitive styles, noetic and epistemological styles.

There are a large number of different cognitive styles classifications, note the most famous, which have become fundamental in creating others:

1) four levels of the conceptual system organization depending on the degree of concepts' differentiation and integration (measures of its "conceptual complexity" growth), to which different social orientations correspond (Harvey et. al., 1961): level I – a positive orientation towards social referents (for example, religious or institutional authorities), benevolence, conformal

type of behavior (pole of “specificity”); level II – negative orientation relative to the same social referents, resistance to social norms of behavior, active authorities rejection, aggression and negativism manifestations (intermediate level); level III – focus on friendships with other people as an attempt to avoid feelings of helplessness and fear of social isolation, developed skills of manipulating communication partners (intermediate level); level IV – focus on one's own internal experience in understanding what is happening, the cognitive orientation predominance, orientation in evaluating other people for their competence (pole of “abstraction”);

2) epistemological styles (Royce & Mos, 1980) – individual-peculiar forms of cognitive attitude to the surrounding world and to oneself as a subject of cognitive activity; three dimensions: the conceptualization degree (events are experienced as differentiated into parts, knowledge is quickly formed into words, thoughts are substantiated – events are experienced as an undifferentiated whole, intuitive assumptions dominate); the theorization degree (abstract approach, reliance on a system of ideas – observation, reliance on a set of facts); the extensiveness degree (coverage of many facts, ideas, diverse interests – analysis of a small number of facts, ideas, concentrated interests).

There are three basic styles of cognition, based on which “images of the world” are built: empiricism (a view of reality is determined by perception and concrete-figurative experience; beliefs are confirmed by raising questions about facts, careful measurements, observations reliability), rationalism (the construction of broad conceptual schemes – “theories”; the adequacy of one's own beliefs is assessed based on logical conclusions and justifications, the consequent stability of the individual image of the world) and metaphorism (the desire for a diversity of impressions, a combination of remote areas of knowledge; a characteristic tendency to symbolize and global understanding of reality; verification of the reliability of the individual image of the world is carried out in terms of intuition);

3) individual-style approach (Witkin & Goodenough, 1982) on 10 dimensions-poles: field dependence/independence; impulsivity/reflectivity; cognitive simplicity/complexity; narrow/wide range of equivalence; narrowness/width of the category; rigid/flexible cognitive control; tolerance for unrealistic experiences; focusing/scanning control; concrete/abstract conceptualization; smoothing/ sharpening;

4) a cyclical four-step empirical model of the learning process and human assimilation of new information (Experiential Learning Model) (Kolb, 1985), in which: the learning process is optimized by integrating the strengths of

behavioral (focus on behavior change by developing new skills and improving existing) and cognitive (focus on the development and improvement of consciousness, taking into account the motivational system) models of learning; provides full rights, equality, a partnership of participants in the learning process, different levels of readiness for active participation in the learning process and motivation to improve their professionalism; four possible ways of cognitive activity through experience, observation, and reflection, with the help of abstract conceptualization, through active experimentation;

5) four learning styles (Honey & Mumford, 1988) based on their diagnosis (Honey Mumford Preferred Learning Style Test): active (satisfaction from solving tasks that require maximum stress, constant readiness to complete the task; conditions for effective learning: a wide range of tasks and opportunities for their solution, freedom to generate ideas), reflective (careful collection and analysis of information; optimal learning conditions: self-control of the learning pace, lack of strict deadlines, enough time to prepare, opportunities to understand reality, summarizing learning), theoretical (integrate and adapt facts and their observations into complex and logically coherent theories, the tendency to systems thinking is manifested in the desire to explore the basic theoretical positions, principles and models; conditions: clearly marked structure, goals and objectives of studying, there is time for the logical construction, events and situations; there is a situation of intellectual tension in which they have to use their skills and knowledge; the material fits into their logical scheme) and pragmatic (the ability to experience new theories and methods in practice, conditions: the subject of research is that which has practical benefits and significance, you can quickly implement the acquired knowledge and skills; the training program involves experiments, practical tasks and consultations with qualified professionals-practices). It is known that each student more or less presents elements of all styles, however, dominant trends determine both the features of the learning process and the reaction to certain methods and efforts of the teacher. It is known that each student, more or less, presents elements of all styles. However, dominant trends determine both the features of the learning process and the reaction to definite methods and efforts of the teacher. In each case, you can build a profile that determines the significance of each style in conjunction with others;

6) four styles of cognition (The Learning Style Inventory (Whetten, n.d.)): divergent (based on specific experience and reflexive observation, characterized by: visualization of specific situations, generation of new ideas and development of alternative perspectives, creative activity, associated with a comprehensive consideration of problems, the search for all sorts of information

and “brainstorming”; the use of induction methods, the breadth of interests; developed imagination, emotionality, value the work associated with live communication), assimilative (reflexive observation and abstract conceptualization; characteristic: processing large amounts of information and presenting it in an accurate, compact and logical form; the use of induction methods, the desire to comprehend all available information; logical perfection of theory put above its practical or applied value; like lectures, reading, work with analytical models and when they have enough time to think, prefer to engage in work, the main element of which is the search, retrieval and analysis of information), convergent (abstract conceptualization and active experimentation; characteristic: skillful use in practice of various ideas and theories; in solving problems and decision-making, they prefer to deal with technical problems and formulated problems rather than issues of social and interpersonal relations; are able to embody ideas in practice and solve problems that are clear to them; usually tend to careers in engineering and technology; prefer to engage in models, laboratory work and practical applications of research results; prefer to deal with purely technical issues) and accommodative (active experimentation and concrete experience; the optimal sphere – the sphere of practical life experience; clearly plan their activities, experiment with something new; rely more on logical analysis than on intuition, have a tendency to solve problems not so much to systematically criticize, how to interact with other people, stand out in activities that require risk and adaptability, such as entrepreneurship, marketing, sales and management, prefer to engage in the distribution of tasks, goal setting and participation in real projects, as well as experimental testing of different approaches to solve the problem, prefer work that contains components of leadership and leadership.

It should be noted that the introduction of knowledge about the cognitive styles features will help to choose the optimal learning nature, assimilation and use of information, the selection of the right people to create an effective training team, that is, to increase the learning effectiveness.

Personality cognitive and stylistic features as an important integration mechanism of professional development and implementation of the manager are: 1) in adaptation to the requirements of communicative and managerial activities in the socio-cultural sphere (adaptation), factors of which are (Kozhevnikov, 2007, pp. 464-481) intellectual abilities, experience, habits, personality traits that are interrelated with the formation of a cognitive style, and can be considered as a kind of adaptation patterns to the environment as a result of interaction between basic individual characteristics (general intelligence) and long-term external factors (education, professional requirements, cultural and social

environment); 2) in the formation of own cognitive style, based on the individuality strengths, taking into account weaknesses (compensation), as well as based on the individual behavioral characteristics (system formation); 3) in the self-expression of one's individuality through a unique way of performing activities or through the manner of behavior; 4) in motivating one's independence, creative initiative and desire for self-realization, actualization of intellectual potential, socio-cultural, life and professional experience; 5) in the involvement of socio-cultural, life and professional experience in the analysis of professional problems, tasks and situations, designing a professional future; 6) in the relationship of new information and reflective-analytical practice of understanding professional situations (Case method), collective search and discussion of solutions to professionally significant problems; 7) in the establishment of professional and social maturity (operations of deduction and induction, analysis and synthesis as directions of development of reflexive-analytical abilities and experience); in the course of reflective-analytical practice to promote the derivation of general principles and patterns (cognitive schemes), which allow to realize the general in the unique and make the best decision in various professional situations; to provide a strong connection of new material with a well-known, well-mastered; 8) taking into account competing motives, incentives and limitations in resources: time, material, financial, psychophysiological in the process of self-development and self-learning; 9) in self-assessment of the formed stereotypes, styles, strategies of thinking and studying (modeling, monitoring, game and reflective-analytical activity) during the decision of professionally significant problems and situations; 10) in self-knowledge of psychological features, limitations, and resources of one's personality for the development of projects of personal and professional development; 11) in overcoming internal resistance in educational and professional growth, development of business and interpersonal relations in the team, which contribute to the social, intellectual and professional development and realization of the future manager personality.

To realize the creative and adaptive future managers studying potential in the process of storing and distributing (dissemination or interconnection) of information, various methods of creative and cognitive activities integration are used: instrumental (group problem solving, actions algorithm definition or set of general rules, observance of which leads to the invention of the optimal solution) and personal (direct the management of their behavior, form self-confidence, a sense of self-power, promote awareness of the limitless opportunities for self-improvement in any area of life) (Kostyuchenko & Dykhnych,

2016, pp. 230-234), which involve different types of thinking (strategic, creative, intuitive, critical, evaluative, visual, figurative, metaphorical).

Based on the typology and basic approaches to the study of cognitive styles and professional development tasks and the future manager personal development, his cognitive competencies (ability: to learn “in context”, new information should be “real” and immediately checked by action/practice with feedback, to the formation of their own opinion, decision-making, comprehensive multi-level problem solving, to critical, flexible, creative and dialectical thinking) we distinguish the following psychological parameters and characteristics: 1) perception field differentiation (objectivity, completeness of the reality cognitive reflection, “field independence”); 2) type of response (stable tendency of the subject to show the reaction of the situation detailed analysis before making a decision; “reflexivity”); 3) cognitive control (effectiveness of overcoming stereotypes, the task speed and accuracy; “flexibility (lability)”); 4) equivalence range (scale for assessing the similarities and differences of the objects; “wide”); 5) differentiation of the category content (a measure of objects subjective differentiation based on conceptual categories; “latitude”); 6) personal constructs (a measure of the subjective experience organization, presented in the form of personal constructs system; “complexity – simplicity”); 7) tolerance measure in situations of uncertainty, ambiguity (“tolerance”); 8) focusing/scanning control (distribution of attention in covering various aspects of the situation; “scanning width”); 9) conceptualization (interpretation (conceptualization) of what is happening, due to the level of development of concepts differentiation and integration within the individual conceptual system; “abstractness – specificity”); 10) preservation of memory material (“smoothing – sharpening”); 11) accommodative style of cognition (clear activities planning, experimenting with something new; relying mainly on intuition, the tendency to use not so much systematic criticism in solving problems as to interact with other people; risk and adaptability, experimental testing of different approaches to solving the problem; components of leadership and management).

It should be noted that the cognitive and stylistic development of the future manager in learning will contribute to: 1) cooperation strategy as a way to enhance cognitive activity based on mutual understanding, collective analysis of the course and results of this activity, distribution of functions, actions, operations, interpersonal relationships (Savchyn, 2007, pp. 406-407); 2) stimulation of different types of mental activity (reasoning, thought, personal reflection) involves educational influences: intellectual means of persuasion (dialogue, story, proof, conversation, debate); emotional, which activate the experiences and feelings of the individual, appeal to his attitude to himself and to the value

orientations, ideals and life beliefs (methods of persuasion, creating educational situations, role play, competition); volitional, aimed at activating and developing the self-regulatory activity of the pupil as a subject of his own life (training, method of exercises (assignments), method of example, system of perspective lines); 3) problem-dialogical methods of notification educational material (method of organizing students' activities based on analytical and synthetic activities, obtaining new knowledge by solving theoretical and practical problems, problem tasks in specially created problem situations, which is realized in reasoning, reflection); 4) interactive learning (purposeful, specially organized joint group activities with feedback between all participants to exchange information, gain experience, “look” at another person as in a mirror) with elements: conversations, discussions, problem lectures, seminars-discussions, question-and-answer seminars, discussions with provocative questions, brainstorming, group solving of specific situations, business, role and didactic games (Kostyuchenko, 2020); 5) modeling – a method of situations scientific research based on the construction and study of models to obtain new information, make decisions, or gain new experience (varieties: systemic, symbolic, spatial, metaphorical, role, self-modeling), aimed at gradually restoring dynamic characteristics the existence of the subject in their development, as well as – to build an adequate means of cognition of the reproduced logic of the phenomenon essence based on such a mechanism as “Double reflection” (Palii, 2010, p. 93); CARUS creative search method (strategy of realization of combinatorial, reconstructive and universal actions, analogies search) (Moliako, 2007).

Thus, the cognitive style of personality is one of the important psychological mechanisms that contributes to the effective organization of the relationship of the future manager's personality with the environment of formation and implementation of his professionalism.

4. Conclusions

As a result of theoretical analysis and systematization of psychological, socio-psychological, organizational-psychological, pedagogical research it was found out:

1. Cognitive styles as individually unique ways of information processing in the form of individual differences in perception, analysis, structuring, categorization, evaluation of reality: associated with cognitive mental processes and intellectual abilities of the individual, with individual style and its manifestations in cognitive cases and intelligence, in social behavior, in self-regulation, in communication, in emotional processes; is a factor in the structure of the

individual, which affects its components with its integrative properties and contributes to the organization of interaction with the environment, educational and cognitive activities and personal growth of the human; form some typical similar and different forms of cognitive response; as the strategy of educational and cognitive activities significantly affects the efficiency of obtaining, processing and transmitting information; most fully realize the professionally necessary abilities in the learning process.

2. Based on different interpretations and provisions of cognitive styles, we have identified them as interpersonal differences in information processing, cognition strategies, cognitive-stylistic dimension of personality depending on the characteristics of its cognitive organization. Those items determine the ways of setting and solving problems, acceptance decisions, and goals. This contributes to the professional formation and development of the future manager as an interactive construct that develops by socio-cultural, educational, professional, and other relevant requirements of society, implements, in particular, in socio-cultural activities. The socio-cultural activity involves planning, coordination, and control of socio-cultural processes carried out by the subjects of socio-cultural activities which provide effective operation of relevant technologies, knowledge, and information, the non-standard vision of new opportunities for professional functioning and development, original ideas production, the flexibility of thinking and behavior.

3. The combination of cognitive and stylistic features against the background of intentional experience, creative thinking realization, with the dominance of certain personality traits, namely creativity, reflectivity, sensuality, activity, associated with increased academic success, the manager adaptation to ever-changing conditions of communication and management, in particular at the stage of its planning, when activating certain information sets, responsible for situation analysis, new information evaluation, research objects choice, landmarks choice, allow to organize “chaos of thinking” and find means and ways of such ordering.

4. On the basis of cognitive styles typologies and formation tasks of cognitive competencies of the future manager of socio-cultural activity, psychological parameters and characteristics are singled out, namely: differentiation of the field of perception – “field independence”; type of response – “reflexivity”; cognitive control – “flexibility”; range of equivalence – “wide”; differentiation of the category content – “latitude”; personal constructs – “complexity”; tolerance measure in situations of uncertainty, ambiguity – “tolerance”; focusing / scanning control – “scanning width”; conceptualization – “specificity”; preservation of memory material – “smoothing – sharpening”; accommodation style of cognition.

5. In the professional education of future managers should be taken into account: age, growths in the cognitive sphere of personality development of the specified age category (early adulthood), in particular: independence, dialectics, flexibility, critical thinking, as well as individual stylistic features of cognitive development of the personality, based on certain characteristics listed in different classifications of cognitive styles, which will help to choose the optimal nature of studying, learning and use of information, creating an effective training team, thus improving the learning efficiency. In the professional training of future managers in the process of storing and distributing information, we consider effective instrumental and personal methods of integration of creative and cognitive activities, which involve different types of thinking, namely: strategic, creative, intuitive, critical, evaluative, visual, visual-effective, metaphorical).

6. Defining in the cognitive-style development of the future manager's personality are cooperation strategy as a way to enhance cognitive activity based on mutual understanding, collective analysis of the course and results of this activity, distribution of functions, actions, operations, interpersonal relationships; stimulation of different types of mental activity, which involves intellectual, emotional, volitional educational influences; problem-dialogue methods of presenting information; interactive learning; modeling; creative search method.

7. As an important integration mechanism of professional formation and development of the manager cognitive and stylistic features of personality are: in adaptation to the requirements of communicative and managerial activities in the socio-cultural sphere; in the formation of their own cognitive style; in the self-expression of one's own individuality through a unique way of performing activities or through the manner of behavior; in motivating one's own self-realization; in attracting socio-cultural, life and professional experience in the analysis of professional problems, tasks and situations, designing a professional future; in the relationship of new information and reflective-analytical practice of understanding professional situations; in self-assessment of formed stereotypes, styles, strategies of thinking and learning; in self-knowledge of psychological features, limitations and resources of one's own personality for the development of projects of personal and professional development; in overcoming internal resistance to learning and professional growth, the development of business and interpersonal relationships in the team, which contributes to the effective organization of the relationship of the future manager with the living and professional environment of its formation and implementation.

The scientific novelty. Scientific approaches to the cognitive styles' definition are systematized, based on which the definition of the cognitive-style component of the personality of the socio-cultural activity manager is synthe-

sized, based on which the professional education parameters are supplemented; optimal parameters and characteristics of cognitive styles for the successful functioning of the manager are highlighted.

The significance of the study. The practical significance of the obtained results consists in the effective application of students' cognitive-style development in the educational process, which made it possible to eliminate a certain deficit of style knowledge on the development of students cognitive activity, as well as to fill the gap of students' knowledge on their cognitive development capabilities. The obtained data were used in the development of specific teaching materials in the disciplines: "Psychology", "Psychology of Management" and "Modern technologies for teaching psychological disciplines".

Prospects for further research. The study does not cover the full depth of the problem. We see the prospects for further research in an empirical study of the relationship between cognitive styles and mental personality traits of the future manager.

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References:

- Bogoyavlenskaya, D. B., & Susokolova, I. A. (2006). K Voprosu o Divergentnom Myishlenii [On the Question of Divergent Thinking]. *Psichologicheskaya Nauka i Obrazovanie [Psychological Science and Education]*, 11(1), 85-96 (in Russ.).
- Bondar, S. (2016). Kohnityvni Styli Osobystosti v Komunikatyvni Diialnosti Studentiv [Cognitive Personality Styles in Students' Communicative Activities]. *Internet-Osvita-Nauka-2016 (ION-2016): Desiata Mizhnarodna Naukovo-Praktychna Konferentsiia [Internet-Education-Science (IES-2016): Tenth International Scientific and Practical Conference]*. Vinnytsia: VNTU, 209-210 (in Ukr.).
- Broverman, D. M. (1960). Dimensions of Cognitive Style. *Journal of Personality*, 28(2), 167-185, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6494.1960.tb01611.x>.
- Bryl, M. (2018). Menedzher Sotsiokulturnoi Diialnosti yak Subiekt Innovatsii [Manager of Social and Cultural Activity as a Subject of Innovation]. *Visnyk Kyivskoho Natsionalnoho Universytetu Kultury i Mystetstv. Serii: Menedzhment Sotsiokulturnoi Diialnosti [Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Management of Social and Cultural Activity]*, 1(1), 41-52, doi: <https://doi.org/10.31866/2616-7573.1.2018.143386> (in Ukr.).

- Craig, G. J., & Baukum, D. (2006). *Psikhooolgiya Razvitiya [Human Development]* (T. V. Prokhorenko, Trans. in Eng.). St. Petersburg: Piter (in Russ.).
- Dorfman, L. Ya., Druzhinina, V. N., & Korostelyanin, K. (1998). *Stil' Cheloveka: Psikhologicheskii Analiz [Human Style: Psychological Analysis]*. Moscow: Smysl (in Russ.).
- Dyba, O. P. (2018). Komunikatyvna Kompetentnist yak Skladova Profesiinosti Menedzhera Kultury [Communicative Competence as a Professional Composition of Manager of Culture]. *Bibliotekoznavstvo. Dokumentoznavstvo. Informolohiia [Library Science. Record Studies. Informology]*, 3, 103-111, doi: <https://doi.org/10.32461/2409-9805.3.2018.150946> (in Ukr.).
- Erikson, E. H. (2006). *Identichnost: Yunost i Krizis [Identity: Youth and Crisis]* (A. V. Tolstykh, Trans. in Eng.). Moscow: Flinta (in Russ.).
- Ermolaeva-Tomina, L. B. (2001). Kreativnost' kak Realizatsiya Potentsial'nykh Vozmozhnostei Cheloveka [Creativity as the Realization of Human Potential]. *Sovremennye Tekhnologii Obucheniya Khudozhestvenno-Graficheskim Distsiplinam [Modern Technologies of Teaching Art and Graphic Disciplines]*. Moscow: Prometei (in Russ.).
- Fedotova, T., & Kulchytska, A. (2020). Osoblyvosti Vyjavu Kohnityvno-Stylovykh Kharakterystyk ta Kreatyvnosti v Publichnykh Sluzhbovtsiv [Features of Manifestation of Cognitive-Stylistic Characteristics and Creativity in Public Servants]. *Psykholohichni Perspektyvy [Psychological Prospects Journal]*, 36, 208-224, doi: <https://doi.org/10.29038/2227-1376-2020-36-208-224> (in Ukr.).
- Galiakberova, A. A., & Galyamova, E. Kh. (2019). Cognitive Styles in Solving Educational Tasks. *Journal of History Culture and Art Research*, 8(4), 371-381, doi: <https://doi.org/10.7596/taksad.v8i4.2385>.
- Gardner, R. W. (1953). Cognitive Style in Categorizing Behavior. *Journal of Personality*, 22, 214-233, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6494.1953.tb01807.x>.
- Gardner, R. W., Jackson, D. N., & Messick, S. J. (1960). Personality Organization in Cognitive Controls and Intellectual Abilities. *Psychological Issues*, 2(8), 149.
- Guilford, J. P. (1958). New Frontiers of Testing in the Discovery and Development of Human Talent. *Seventh Annual Western Regional Conference on Testing Problems*. Los Angeles, 20-32.
- Guseva, T. A. (2009). Stili Poznavatel'noi Aktivnosti Lichnosti Studentov [Styles of Cognitive Activity of Students' Personality]. *PhD Dissertation*. Novosibirsk: Novosibirsk State Pedagogical University (in Russ.).
- Harvey, O. J., Hunt, D. E., & Schroder, H. M. (1961). *Conceptual Systems and Personality Organization*. New York: Wiley.
- Honey, P., & Mumford, A. (1988). *The Manual of Learning Styles*. London: Peter Honey Associates.

- Hryhorchuk, T. V. (2018). Formuvannia Profesiohram Menedzheriv Sotsiokulturnoi Sfery [Manager's of Socio-Cultural Sphere Professiogram Developing]. *Visnyk Kyivskoho Natsionalnoho Universytetu Kultury i Mystetstv. Seriya: Menedzhment Sotsiokulturnoi Diialnosti [Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Management of Social and Cultural Activity]*, 1(2), 90-106, doi: <https://doi.org/10.31866/2616-7573.2.2018.149468> (in Ukr.).
- Hurch, L. (2006). Perspektyvy Pidhotovky Konkurentospromozhnykh Menedzheriv u Konteksti Formuvannia Zahalnoievropeiskoho Osvitnoho Prostoru [Prospects for Training Competitive Managers in the Context of the Formation of a Pan-European Educational Space]. *Personal [Personnel]*, 6, 11-16 (in Ukr.).
- Kagan, J. (1966). Reflection-Impulsivity: The Generality and Dynamics of Conceptual Tempo. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*, 71(1), 17-24, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0022886>.
- Kalamazh, R. V. (2012). Kohnityvno-Stylovyi Vymir u Psykholohichnykh Doslidzhenniakh [Cognitive-Stylistic Dimension in Psychological Research]. *Naukovi Zapysky Natsionalnoho Universytetu "Ostrozka Akademiia". Seriya "Psykholohiia i Pedagogika" [Scientific Notes of the National University "Ostroh Academy". Series "Psychology and Pedagogy"]*, 20, 32-41 (in Ukr.).
- Karamushka, L. M., Fil, O. A., & Bleshmudt, P. P. (2012). Kohnityvnyi Komponent Psykholohichnoi Hotovnosti do Roboty v Komandi Personalu Bankivskykh Struktur: Riven i Chynnyky Rozvytku [Cognitive Component of Psychological Readiness to Work in a Team of Staff of Banking Structures: Level and Factors of Development]. *Pravnychiy Visnyk Universytetu "KROK" [Legal Bulletin of KROK University]*, 11, 109-117 (in Ukr.).
- Karpov, A. V. (2004). *Psikhologiya Refleksivnykh Mekhanizmov Deyatel'nosti [Psychology of Reflexive Mechanisms of Activity]*. Moscow: Institute of Psychology of Russian Academy of Sciences (in Russ.).
- Kholodnaya, M. A. (2004). *Kognitivnye Stili: O Prirode Individual'nogo Uma [Cognitive Styles: On the Nature of the Individual Mind]*. St. Petersburg: Piter (in Russ.).
- Kholodnaya, M. A. (1989). Tipy Intellektualnoy Aktivnosti: Stilevyie i Produktivnyie Charakteristiki [Types of Intellectual Activity: Style and Productivity Characteristics]. *Psihologo-Pedagogicheskie Problemy Vysshhey i Sredney Shkoly. [Psychological and Pedagogical Problems of Higher and Secondary Schools]*. Tomsk, 19-33 (in Russ.).
- Klaus, G. (1987). *Vvedenie v Differentsial'nuyu Psikhologiyu Ucheniya [Introduction to Differential Psychology of Learning]* (E. Yu. Patyaeva, Trans. in Germ.). Moscow: Pedagogika (in Russ.).
- Kolb, A. Y., & Kolb, D. A. (2009). The Learning Way: Meta-Cognitive Aspects of Experiential Learning. *Simulation & Gaming*, 40(3), 297-327, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1046878108325713>.

- Kolb, D. A. (1985). *Learning Style Inventory*. Boston: Hay Group.
- Kornilova, T. V., & Paramei, G. V. (1989). Podkhody k Izucheniyu Kognitivnykh Stilei: Dvadsat' Let Spustya [Approaches to Studying Cognitive Styles: Twenty Years Later]. *Voprosy Psikhologii [Psychology Issues]*, 6, 140-147 (in Russ.).
- Kostiuk, H. S. (1989). *Navchalno-Vykhovnyi Protses i Psykhichni Rozvytok Osobystosti [Educational Process and Mental Development of Personality]*. Kyiv: Radianska Shkola (in Ukr.).
- Kostruba, N. (2020). Kohnityvno-Stylova Kharakterystyka Komunikatyvnoi Kompetentnosti Studenta [Cognitive Style and Communicative Competence of Students]. *Psykholohichni Perspektyvy [Psychological Prospects Journal]*, 35, 68-82, doi: <https://doi.org/10.29038/2227-1376-2020-35-68-82> (in Ukr.).
- Kostiuchenko, O. V. (2017). Psykholohichni Suprovid Profesiinoi Realizatsii Fakhivtsia Industrii Mody [Psychological Support of Professional Realization of a Specialist in the Fashion Industry]. *Psykholohichni Chasopys [Psychological Journal]*, 3(1), 86-96 (in Ukr.).
- Kostiuchenko, O. V. (2018a). Psykholohichna Hotovnist Menedzhera do Upravlinnia Proektnoiu Diialnistiu [Psychological Readiness of the Manager for Project Activity Management]. *Visnyk Kyivskoho Natsionalnoho Universytetu Kultury i Mystetstv. Seriya: Menedzhment Sotsiokulturnoi Diialnosti [Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Management of Social and Cultural Activity]*, 1(1), 25-41 (in Ukr.).
- Kostiuchenko, O. V. (2018b). Psykholoho-Pedahohichni Suprovid Samorozvytku Osobystosti Maibutnoho Fakhivtsia Industrii Mody [Psychological and Pedagogical Support of the Self-Development of the Personality of the Future Specialist of the Fashion Industry]. *Modern Education Space: the Transformation of National Models in Terms of Integration: II International Scientific Conference*. Leipzig: Leipzig University, 114-117 (in Ukr.).
- Kostiuchenko, O. V. (2018c). Vyznachalni Sotsialno-Psykholohichni Faktory Efektyvnoho Upravlinnia Komandoiu [Determining Socio-Psychological Factors of Effective Team Management]. *Psykholoho-Pedahohichni Problemy Stanovlennia Suchasnoho Fakhivtsia: IV Mizhnarodna Naukovo-Praktychna Konferentsiia [Psychological and Pedagogical Problems of Modern Specialist Formation: IV International Scientific and Practical Conference]*. Kharkiv: KhOHOKZ, 42-48, doi: <https://doi.org/10.26697/9786177089017.2018.42> (in Ukr.).
- Kostiuchenko, O. V. (2019). Metaforyzatsiia yak Psykholohichni Resurs Potentsiinosti Maibutnoho Fakhivtsia [Metaphorization as a Psychological Resource of Potentiality of the Future Specialist]. *International Journal of Education and Science*, 2(2), 49, doi: <https://doi.org/10.26697/ijes.2019.2.35> (in Ukr.).
- Kostiuchenko, O. V., & Dykhnych, L. P. (2016). *Psykholohiia Efektyvnosti Fakhivtsia Industrii Mody [Psychology of Efficiency of a Specialist in the Fashion Industry]*. Kyiv: Lira-K (in Ukr.).

- Kostiuchenko, O. V. (2020). Psykholoho-Pedahohichni Skladovi v Systemi Suchasnykh Tekhnolohii Navchannia u Vyshi [Psychological and Pedagogical Components in the System of Modern Technologies of Higher Education]. *Problemy ta Perspektyvy Rozvytku Suchasnoi Nauky v Krainakh Yevropy ta Azii: XXX Mizhnarodna Naukovo-Praktychna Internet-Konferentsiia [Problems and Prospects for the Development of Modern Science in Europe and Asia: XXX International Scientific and Practical Internet Conference]*. Pereiaslav: Hryhorii Skovoroda University in Pereiaslav, 110-112, Retrieved from http://conferences.neasmo.org.ua/uploads/conference/file/80/conference_30-30.9.2020.pdf (in Ukr.).
- Kozhevnikov, M. (2007). Cognitive Styles in the Context of Modern Psychology: Toward an Integrated Framework of Cognitive Style. *Psychological Bulletin*, 133(3), 464-481, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.133.3.464>.
- Kutsenko L. M. (2002). Kohnityvnyi Styl yak Instrument Strukturuvannia Piznavalnoho Dosvidu Osobystosti [Cognitive Style as a Tool for Structuring the Cognitive Experience of the Individual]. *Problemy Zahalnoi ta Pedahohichnoi Psykholohii [Problems of General and Pedagogical Psychology]*, 3(9), 30-40 (in Ukr.).
- Liedtke, J., & Fromhage, L. (2019). Modelling the Evolution of Cognitive Styles. *BMC Evolutionary Biology*, 19, 234, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12862-019-1565-2>.
- Lysakova, I. (2013). Indyvidualno-Psykholohichni Peredumovy Pidhotovky Menedzhera Sotsiokulturnoi Diialnosti [Individual-Psychological Prerequisites of Training the Manager of Social and Cultural Activity]. *Visnyk Instytutu Rozvytku Dytyny [Bulletin of the Institute of Child Development]*, 28, 158-162 (in Ukr.).
- Maksymenko, S. D. (2006). *Geneza Zdiisnennia Osobystosti [Genesis of Personality Realization]*. Kyiv: KMM (in Ukr.).
- Maksymenko, S. D., & Pasichnyk, I. D. (2010). Rol Kohnityvno-Stylovykh Osoblyvostei Osobystosti v Protsesi Navchalnoi Diialnosti [The Role of Cognitive and Stylistic Features of the Individual in the Learning Process]. *Naukovi Zapysky Natsionalnoho Universytetu "Ostrozka Akademiia". Seriia "Psykholohiia i Pedahohika" [Scientific Notes of the National University "Ostroh Academy". Series "Psychology and Pedagogy"]*, 14, 3-10 (in Ukr.).
- Martynyshyn, Ya. M., & Kostyuchenko, O. V. (2018). Proektnyi Menedzhment yak Stratehichnyi Instrument Rozvytku Sotsiokulturnoi Sfery [Project Management as Strategic Instrument for Socio-Cultural Sphere Development]. *Visnyk Natsionalnoi Akademii Kerivnykh Kadriv Kultury i Mystetstv [National Academy of Managerial Staff of Culture and Arts Herald]*, 4, 84-89 (in Ukr.).

- Martynyshyn, Ya. M., & Kovalenko, Ye. Ya. (2018). *Mystetstvo Upravlinnia y Osvitni Tekhnologii Pidhotovky Menedzheriv Sotsiokulturnoi Diialnosti [Art of Management and Educational Technologies of Training of Managers of Social and Cultural Activity]*. Bila Tserkva: Publisher Pshonkivskiyi O.V. (in Ukr.).
- Moliako, V. (2004). Psykholohichna Teoriia Tvorchosti [Psychological Theory of Creativity]. *Obdarovana Dytyna [Gifted child]*, 6, 2-9 (in Ukr.).
- Moliako, V. (2007). *Tvorcheskaya Konstruktsiia (Prolegomeny) [Creative Constructology (Prolegomena)]*. Kyiv: Osvita Ukrainy (in Russ.).
- Molyako, V.A. (1994)/ Problemyi psihologii tvorchestva i razrobotka podhoda k izucheniyu odarenosti [Problems of the psychology of creativity and the development of an approach to the study of giftedness]. *Voprosy psihologii [Psychology issues]*, 5, 86-95. (in Russ.).
- Morosanova, V. I. (2010). Individual'nye Osobennosti Osoznannoi Samoregulyatsii Proizvol'noi Aktivnosti Cheloveka [Individual Characteristics of Conscious Self-Regulation of Voluntary Human Activity]. *Vestnik Moskovskogo Universiteta. Seriya 14. Psikhologiya [Moscow University Psychology Bulletin]*, 1, 36-45 (in Russ.).
- Moskalov, M. V. (2015). Psykholohichni Suprovid Vkhodzhennia Molodykh Pedahohiv v Osvitniu Orhanizatsiiu [Psychological Support of Young Teachers Entering an Educational Organization]. *ScienceRise*, 11(1), 69-74, doi: <https://doi.org/10.15587/2313-8416.2015.53479> (in Ukr.).
- Naprasna, O. B. (2004). Indyvidualno-Psykholohichni Osoblyvosti Kohnityvno-Stylovykh Kharakterystyk Navchalnoi Diialnosti Studentiv [Individual-Psychological Features of Cognitive-Stylistic Characteristics of Students' Educational Activity]. PhD Dissertation. Kyiv: Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv (in Ukr.).
- Olenina, O. Yu. (2013). Kontsepsiia Pidhotovky Menedzheriv Sotsiokulturnoi Diialnosti v Umovakh Formuvannia Suspilstva Znan [The Concept of Training of Managers of Social and Cultural Activity in the Conditions of Formation of a Knowledge Society]. *Kultura Ukrainy [Culture of Ukraine]*, 42(2), 41-49 (in Ukr.).
- Palii, A. A. (2010) *Dyferentsialna Psykholohiia [Differential Psychology]*, 2nd ed. Kyiv: Akademvydav (in Ukr.).
- Palii, A. A. (2011). Kohnityvni Styli yak Determinanty Formuvannia Osobystisnykh Rys [Cognitive Styles as Determinants of Personality Traits]. *Zbirnyk Naukovykh Prats: Filosofiia, Sotsiologiia, Psykholohiia [Collection of Scientific Works: Philosophy, Sociology, Psychology]*, 16(2), 58-65 (in Ukr.).
- Petrova, I. V. (2019). Profesiina Pidhotovka Ivent-Menedzheriv u Konteksti Dualnoi Formy Zdobuttia Osvity [Professional Training of Event-Managers in the Context of Dual Form of Acquiring Education]. *Visnyk Kyivskoho Natsionalnoho Universytetu Kultury i Mystetstv. Seriya: Menedzhment Sotsiokulturnoi Diialnosti [Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Management of Social and Cultural Activity]*, 2(1), 82-104, doi: <https://doi.org/10.31866/2616-7573.1.2019.170657> (in Ukr.).

- Pisotskyi, O. P. (2008). Kohnityvnyi Styl yak Chynnyk Rozvytku Intelktualnoho Potentsialu Maibutnoho Praktychnoho Psykholoha [Cognitive Style as a Factor in the Development of the Intellectual Potential of the Future Practical Psychologist]. *Abstract of PhD Dissertation*. Kyiv: National Pedagogical Dragomanov University (in Ukr.).
- Polishchuk, V. M. (2007). *Vikova i Pedahohichna Psykholohiia [Age and Pedagogical Psychology]*. Sumy: Universytetska knyha (in Ukr.).
- Ponomarenko, V. S. (2012). *Problemy Pidhotovky Kompetentnykh Ekonomistiv ta Menedzheriv v Ukraini [Problems of Training Competent Economists and Managers in Ukraine]*. Kharkiv: INZhEK (in Ukr.).
- Riegel, K. F. (1975). Toward a Dialectical Theory of Development. *Human Development, 18(1-2)*, 50-64, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1159/000271475>.
- Riegel, K. F. (1979). *Foundations of Dialectical Psychology*. New York: Academic Press.
- Rogers, C. R., & Freiberg, H. J. (1994). *Freedom to Learn*, 3-rd ed. New York: Merrill; Toronto: Maxwell Macmillan.
- Romanovska, L. I. (2005). Kohnityvnyi Styl Osobystosti yak Chynnyk Protsesu Rozuminnia Tekstu [Cognitive Style of Personality as a Factor in the Process of Understanding the Text]. *Abstract of PhD Dissertation*. Kyiv: G. S. Kostiuk Institute of Psychology of the NAES of Ukraine (in Ukr.).
- Royce, J. R., & Mos, L. P. (1980). *Manual: Psycho-Epistemological Profile*. University of Alberta.
- Savchyn, M. V. (2007). *Pedahohichna Psykholohiia [Pedagogical Psychology]*. Kyiv: Akademvydav (in Ukr.).
- Sheiko, E. P. (2009). Profesiina Pidhotovka Menedzheriv yak Faktor Formuvannia Zdatnosti do Spilnoi Upravlinskoi Diialnosti [Professional Training of Managers as a Factor in the Formation of the Ability to Joint Management Activities]. *Teoretychni i Prykladni Problemy Psykholohii [Theoretical and Applied Problems of Psychology], 1 (21)*, 245-251 (in Ukr.).
- Skorynina, O. V. (2000). Kohnityvnyi Styl ta Piznavalni Protsesy [Cognitive Style and Cognitive Processes]. *Visnyk Kharkivskoho Derzhavnoho Pedahohichnoho Universytetu imeni H. S. Skovorody. Psykholohiia [Bulletin of H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv State Pedagogical University. Psychology], 4(13)*, 119-123 (in Ukr.).
- Sternberg, R. J. (2001). What is the Common Thread of Creativity? Its Dialectical Relation to Intelligence and Wisdom. *American Psychologist, 56(4)*, 360-362, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.56.4.360>.
- Sternberg, R. J. (Ed.). (2002). *Prakticheskii Intellekt [Practical Intelligence in Everyday Life]* (Trans. in Eng.). St. Petersburg: Piter (in Russ.).
- Studenikin, A. A. (1999). Vplyv Kohnityvnoho Styliu Osobystosti na Protses Spilkuvannia [The Influence of Cognitive Style of Personality on the Process of Communication]. *Abstract of PhD Dissertation*. Kyiv: G. S. Kostiuk Institute of Psychology of the NAES of Ukraine. (in Ukr.).
- Tokareva, N. M., & Shamne, A. V. (2017). *Vikova ta Pedahohichna Psykholohiia [Age and Pedagogical Psychology]*. Kyiv (in Ukr.).

- Tolochek, V. A. (2013). *Problema Stilei v Psikhologii: Istoriko-Teoreticheskii Analiz [The Problem of Styles in Psychology: Historical and Theoretical Analysis]*. Moscow: Institute of Psychology of Russian Academy of Science (in Russ).
- Torrance, E. P. (1964). *Guiding Creative Talent*. New York: Prentice Hall.
- Torrance, E. P. (1979). *The Search for Satori and Creativity*. New York: Creative Education Foundation.
- Vygotsky, L. S. (2003). *Psikhologiya Razvitiya Cheloveka [Psychology of Human Development]*. Moscow: Eksmo-Press (in Russ.).
- Wang, D., Hao, L., Maguire, P., Hu, Y. (2018). The effects of cognitive style and emotional trade-off difficulty on information processing in decision-making. *International Journal of Psychology, 53*(6), 468-476, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijop.12404>.
- Wardell, D. M., & Royce, J. R. (1978). Toward a Multi-Factor Theory of Styles and Their Relationships to Cognition and Affect. *Journal of Personality, 46*(3), 474-505, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6494.1978.tb01013.x>.
- Whetten, D. A. (n.d.). *Opredelenie Vashego Stilya Poznaniya po Metodu LSI [Determination of Your Learning Style According to the LSI Method]*, Retrieved from <http://www.elitarium.ru/stil-obuchenie-informaciya-poznanie-put-issledovanie-opyt-problema-nablyudenie-ehksperimentirovanie-abstraktnaya-rezultat/>
- Witkin, H. A., & Dyk, R. B., Faterson, H. F., Goodenough, D. R., & Karp, S. A. (1962). *Psychological Differentiation*. New York, London: John Wiley & Sons.
- Witkin, H. A., & Goodenough, D. R. (1982). Cognitive Style: Essence and Origins. *Psychological Issues, 51*, 1-141.
- Zhang, M., Wang, X., Wang, F., & Liu, H. (2020). Effect of Cognitive Style on Language Control During Joint Language Switching: an ERP Study. *Journal of Psycholinguistic Research, 49*(3), 383-400, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10936-019-09682-7>.
- Zherdetska, L. L. (2006). Kohnityvni Styli yak Chynnyk Profesiinoho Stanovlennia Maibutnikh Psykholohiv [Cognitive Styles as a Factor in the Professional Development of Future Psychologists]. *Abstract of PhD Dissertation*. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University (in Ukr.).

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